

International Peer Review Journal

p-ISSN 1817-5562

e-ISSN 1998-037X (Online)

CD-ROM ISSN 1998-0361

**The New Iraqi Journal Of Medicine
The Official Journal Of The Iraqi Ministry Of Health
and Iraq Headquarter of Copernicus Scientists
International Panel**

Volume 7 Number 1 April 2011

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer-review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

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Indexed by Copernicus Index Journal Master List and EMR index medicus

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Therapeutic advances in renal cell carcinoma

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Abstract

Renal cell carcinoma (RCC) continues to represent an important proportion of the cancer landscape in many countries. The mainstay of treatment is radical nephrectomy for localized disease, and until recently, the treatment options for patients with either unresectable or metastatic renal cell carcinoma were limited. Important therapeutic advances in the management of patients with advanced renal cell carcinoma have occurred during the previous decades. Prior to the advent of targeted therapy, the prognosis of patients with metastatic renal cell carcinoma was very poor, with a median survival of one year and a five-year survival of 0%–20%.

The landscape for renal cell carcinoma treatment has changed dramatically in recent years, with the addition of three new FDA-approved agents this year. This brings our arsenal to seven drugs: interleukin-2, the VEGF receptor TKI's sunitinib, sorafenib, and pazopanib, the VEGF neutralizing antibody bevacizumab in combination with interferon, and the mTOR inhibitors temsirolimus and everolimus. The aim of this paper is to briefly review the important therapeutic advances in RCC.

The N Iraqi J Med, April 2011;7(3):91-95

Keywords: RCC, new agents, therapeutic advances

Renal cell carcinoma (RCC) continues to represent an important proportion of the cancer landscape in many countries [1,2,3]. The mainstay of treatment is radical nephrectomy for localized disease, and until recently, the treatment options for patients with either unresectable or metastatic renal cell carcinoma were limited. Important therapeutic advances in the management of patients with advanced renal cell carcinoma have occurred during the previous decades. Prior to the advent of targeted therapy, the prognosis of patients with metastatic renal cell carcinoma was very poor, with a median survival of one year and a five-year survival of 0%–20% [4].

One of the major achievements was the recognition that RCC is not a single disease but a compilation of different histologic types, each caused by different

genetic mutations affecting different molecular pathways. In fact, four distinct genes have now been well described as a cause for the different types of RCC. Understanding of these genetic alterations and pathways has resulted in several new medications approved for use in the treatment of metastatic RCC and many more in clinical trials at the present time [5, 13].

The landscape for renal cell carcinoma treatment has changed dramatically in recent years, with the addition of three new FDA-approved agents this year. This brings our arsenal to seven drugs: interleukin-2, the VEGF receptor TKI's sunitinib, sorafenib, and pazopanib, the VEGF neutralizing antibody bevacizumab in combination with interferon, and the mTOR inhibitors temsirolimus and everolimus. Treatment of metastatic renal cell carcinoma involved immunotherapeutic agents such as interferon (IFN- α) or interleukin-2 (IL-2). IFN- α has been shown to provide a benefit in terms of overall survival compared to inactive therapy but with an average response rate between 10%–15%

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and few durable responses. High dose IL-2 (infusion therapy requiring hospitalization) has a higher overall and complete response (CR) rate compared with low-dose cytokines (subcutaneous, outpatient), with the real benefit realized in the small percentage (5% to 7%) of patients who experience adurable CR. The patient most likely to obtain a durable CR with high-dose IL-2 includes the young, previously untreated patient with clear-cell histology RCC, ECOG performance status 0, and limited volume metastatic disease to lung. The morbidity and lack of applicability of high dose IL-2 to the broad RCC population has dampened enthusiasm for this approach, although it remains a valid treatment option in a very limited subset of patients [14, 15].

Adjuvant and neoadjuvant treatments for RCC represent an important opportunity for reducing the risk of disease recurrence, and potentially expanding the group of patients cured of this cancer. Adjuvant trials of cytokine-based therapies have been disappointing, demonstrating lack of improvement over surgical treatment alone, or in some cases trends toward shortened survival [16, 17]. Recent efforts to implement novel strategies of immune system modulation have been the first to demonstrate a potential for improved outcome. In the 10-year survival analysis of a study of autologous tumor lysate vaccine adjuvant therapy, a trend was showed toward increased survival in all patients, with a statistically significant improvement observed for patients with T3 tumors. In multivariate analysis, the T3 tumor subgroup continued to demonstrate improved survival, HR=1.67, p=0.011 [18]. In a move toward advancing targeted anti-angiogenesis therapy to the adjuvant setting, a small study was performed at MD Anderson Cancer Center exploring the use of adjuvant thalidomide. Forty six patients were enrolled to a randomized study of observation vs. thalidomide 300mg daily for 24 months. The two- and three-year cancer-specific survivals were not improved with treatment, and the thalidomide-treated patients actually had poorer survival at two and three years (47.8% vs. 69.3% and 28.7% vs. 69.3%, respectively; P = .022) [19].

Much attention is being focused on several ongoing studies testing the adjuvant use of VEGF receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitor (TKI) therapy. Despite the failure of thalidomide to demonstrate activity in this venue, evidence from the metastatic disease setting suggests that the VEGF-receptor TKIs are much more potent against RCC. Multiple studies are ongoing and anticipated to complete enrollment in the coming year. These studies include: the ASSURE study, randomizing patients with completely resected clear cell tumor larger than 4cm to 1 year of sunitinib, sorafenib, or placebo, at conventional

doses; the SORCE study, randomizing completely resected RCC tumors (any histology) in Europe that are intermediate or high risk according to the Leibovich score [20] to one year or three years of sorafenib at standard dose, or placebo; and finally, a smaller study comparing standard dose sunitinib to placebo (randomized 2:1) . While these studies will take time to fully mature, they will provide immediate demonstration of the acute and longer term side effects of prolonged therapy in otherwise quite healthy individuals, and ultimately represent the most promising avenue of potential risk reduction for patients facing high risk for recurrence.

With drugs that can induce initial tumor shrinkage, it has become relevant to determine whether implementation of pre-operative treatment can impact primary tumors to reduce tumor bulk prior to surgery. Such an intervention may permit less invasive surgical approaches, or render "unresectable" disease "resectable," or provide an opportunity to gain control of systemic disease prior to removal of the primary mass. Several studies have begun to evaluate these approaches. The use of bevacizumab was investigated in the pre-operative setting for patients undergoing cytoreductive nephrectomy. This study of 50 patients showed responses in the primary tumor, but led to wound dehiscence in three patients, likely due to the long half life of the antibody [21]. Retrospective studies of a variety of VEGF pathway targeted agents with widely varied durations of therapy prior to surgery showed the approach was feasible [22, 23]. Sunitinib treatment until best response was employed in 19 patients with inoperable tumors, with four proceeding to nephrectomy without encountering any unexpected surgical morbidity [24]. A prospective study using sorafenib in a 4-8 week window prior to surgery and continuing to within 48 hours of surgery defined the safety risks, which were minimal, and showed a response in the primary tumor similar to that observed for systemic disease [25]. This study also highlighted the necessity for pretreatment biopsy, as two of the 30 patients on the study were found at nephrectomy to have non-renal cell primary tumors. Overall, these approaches are rational to consider for selected patients, appear to pose minimal risk for decline in performance status for surgery, and can achieve responses in primary tumors. Further investigation is necessary to determine the patient groups most likely to benefit from neoadjuvant therapy, and whether risk for disease recurrence can be reduced. In addition, the optimal duration of treatment prior to surgery needs to be defined.

Sunitinib has emerged as the current standard of care for first line therapy for patients with good or intermediate risk clear cell RCC. However, sorafenib remains an appropriate first line choice for selected

patients, and recently pazopanib has received FDA approval, adding a third agent in this crowded field. With prolonged experience and exposure to these drugs, cardiac toxicity related to sunitinib has become a concern. Patients with pre-existing hypertension and coronary heart disease compose the group at greatest risk for encountering these effects [26]. Preclinical analysis suggests that sunitinib may be directly toxic to cardiac myocytes [27]. The lasting effects of sunitinib exposure to endothelial and other tissues remain largely unknown. It is concerning that administration of high dose IL-2 after sunitinib failure has showed a high incidence of severe cardiac toxicity, suggesting that damage may remain for some time after TKI therapy is discontinued [28]. Ultimately, what is becoming clear is the need to aggressively manage toxicities in order to maintain patients on optimally dosed therapy and avoid detrimental long-term complications [29, 30].

Effective disease control has been inferred from significant improvements in progression-free survival. Now with more substantial follow up, the front-line study of sunitinib vs. interferon has showed an overall survival benefit (26.4 v 21.8 months, $p = 0.51$), even in the setting of 65% of the interferon patients crossing over to receive sunitinib or another VEGF pathway targeted agent [31]. This survival benefit is modest, but suggests that additional consideration to questions such as when to initiate therapy (early vs. late) may be important to investigate formally.

RCCs initially responding to treatment with VEGF TKI therapy eventually develops resistance to these drugs is also of considerable importance. Kinase mutations that cause resistance to drugs like imatinib do not appear to play a role here. Ongoing studies suggest angiogenic escape mechanisms may contribute to this process [32]. One experiment examining xenografts resistant to sorafenib showed that they regain sensitivity when transplanted into new hosts [33].

An alternate mechanism of targeted therapy for RCC is the inhibition of mTOR signaling via disruption of the mTORC1 complex. While the activities of mTOR inhibitors (temsirolimus and everolimus being the only rapalogues approved for RCC) on cancer cells remains an active area of investigation, we have learned how to strategically place them in the treatment of RCC patients. In the front line setting, temsirolimus has continued to be the mainstay for patients with poor risk disease, given the improvement in overall survival and its good side effect profile [34]. This year everolimus was approved based on a study that evaluated this drug after disease progression on one or both VEGF receptor TKIs [35, 36]. Patients showed a

doubling of progression-free survival. Thus, the mTOR pathway provides an ideal scenario for switching drug classes upon disease progression.

Combining two or more agents has employed two basic approaches. "Vertical inhibition" describes combinations of therapies that target factors working in a linear signaling pathway, as opposed to "Lateral inhibition" which implies inhibiting targets from non-overlapping pathways [37]. The first example of vertical inhibition showed that maximally inhibiting the VEGF signaling pathway with bevacizumab.

inhibition of soluble VEGF ligand in combination with inhibition of VEGF receptor signaling with sorafenib could increase response rate, but at the expense of increased toxicity [38].

Lateral inhibition takes the form of combinations of VEGF targeted agents and mTOR inhibitors. The combination of sunitinib with temsirolimus unfortunately showed unacceptable toxicity, particularly a high incidence of microangiopathic hemolytic anemia [39]. Bevacizumab has been amenable to combinations in many settings, and tolerable doses have been identified for combination with temsirolimus; an ongoing study is evaluating the bevacizumab/temsirolimus combination vs. bevacizumab/interferon.

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